

ბიზნეს პროცესები და მათი ტრანსფორმაცია თანამედროვე კომპანიებში

გოგაშვილი თ.

ბიზნეს ადმინისტრირების დოქტორი
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BUSINESS PROCESSES AND THEIR TRANSFORMATION IN MODERN COMPANIES

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ნაშრომში განხილულია ცვლილების თეორიის შესწავლის ობიექტი, ანუ ორგანიზაციის ტრანსფორმაციისთვის მიღებული ზომების ერთობლიობა, რომელსაც კომპანია ახორციელებს გრძელვადიან პერსპექტივაში და სრულად შეესაბამება მის სტრატეგიულ მიზნებსა და ამოცანებს. ამ მხრივ, ნაშრომში ცვლილებების თეორია განიხილება, როგორც სოციალურ-ეკონომიკური ტრანსფორმაციის პროცესი, რომელზეც მას ძალუძს ზეგავლენა. თავისი მნიშვნელობით, ის აუცილებელია მიკრო და მაკრო დონეზე, ესე იგი როგორც თავად ორგანიზაციისთვის, ასევე ქვეყნის ეკონომიკური ზრდისთვის.

Abstract

The paper examines the object of study of the theory of change, that is, a set of measures taken to transform an organization, which are carried out by the company in the long term and are entirely consistent with its strategic goals and objectives. In this regard, the theory of change is considered in the paper as a process of socio-economic transformation, which can be affected. In its importance, it is necessary at the micro and macro levels, that is, both for the organization itself and for the economic growth of the country.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ბიზნეს პროცესები, ორგანიზაციული ცვლილებები, სტრატეგიული მიზნები, თანამედროვე კომპანიები.

Keywords: business processes, organizational changes, strategic goals, modern companies.

Introduction

Improving the management of economic processes is also achieved by reforming existing organizations and their interconnections. The main content of the reform theory is the understanding that, like any innovation, economic transformations in the form of creating and changing organizational structures, decision-making methods, and forms of incentives must first be developed, mastered, and disseminated by specialists, taking into account human interests, social conditions, and existing limitations. In general, the problems of organizational changes and business process transformation are currently being actively studied by Georgian and foreign specialists. A study of the scientific literature created around this issue has revealed a trend that indicates attempts to develop a new theory that would combine various research tools within its framework - reengineering, "kaizen", outsourcing, etc.

The purpose of the study is to assess the transformation of business processes in the organization, and the research methods used are: reflection of reality, comprehensive and multifaceted study, deduction-induction, and qualitative methods. In addition, we used the dialectical techniques of determinism and contradiction. After selecting the process and considering its characteristics, a set of tools was selected.

Results and Their Assessment

As a natural social process, reformation is an activity of renewal, a transformation of the economic system. The primary methods of such transformations are

modifying the system's elements and enriching it with new knowledge.

From an instrumental point of view, reform is a set of measures taken by the managers of a company or organization, which is logically preceded by specially developed measures and is accompanied by the implementation process. (1, p.3)

In practice, the theory of reform represents the principles by which the processes of transformation and renewal are managed. Change management, like other areas of management, consists of four stages of implementation:

1. Informational and methodological training;
2. Identification of the organization and its conditions;
3. Implementation;
4. Leadership and control. (5, p.8)

The cornerstone of the change system is the definition of tasks. Tasks are goals that are desirable to achieve at a certain point in time within the strategic planning period. For reforms, as a system of large-scale social transformations, a critical condition is the dialectic of combining goals and objectives to be implemented. At a particular stage of the reforms, strategic goals are unattainable, but a step-by-step approach must be taken to achieve them. Therefore, a precise formulation of all goals and objectives is essential, with the existence of criteria for assessing progress in the implementation of each of them. During the implementation of reforms, there should be an opportunity to

combine accents in solving different tasks to overcome possible contradictions and conflicts between tasks, that is, to decide what to do when the implementation of one task contradicts another.

At the enterprise level, reforms can be understood as a significant, purposeful change that introduces new stable elements into the organization (in its goals, technology, economy, organization, etc.), which are subsequently reproduced. Thus, reforms are not considered as separate, unique management measures that are of a unified nature, but as sequential actions that transform the existing order. (2, p.9)

Reforms have their content, which is manifested at different stages of implementation, and many special criteria determine their typological grouping.

The objective reasons for anti-reform behavior are the contradictions of transformations that are inherent in socio-economic systems, and which cannot be overcome. The social nature of the course of economic transformations implies the existence of social groups that are interested in maintaining the existing order, no matter how problematic it may be.

In any environment, there are social groups that are objectively connected with the past and see their advantage in preserving it.

The considered directions of unacceptability of reforms are only part of the resistance to changes and transformations, which is manifested in practice in several measures taken that are directly anti-reformative. (11, p.32)

Anti-reform reactions are manifested both in the activities of administrative bodies in general and in the work of individual performers. The following are actions that hinder the development of reforms:

1. Documentary detailing and formalization of the reform;
2. Partial implementation of reforms;
3. Formal reformation.
4. Obstruction of the design or experimental part of the reform.
5. Introduction of new processes in parallel with the functioning of existing ones. (8, p.13)

In the process of making and implementing various decisions, the structure of the enterprise is transformed and adapts to external influences. Even when an enterprise consciously resists internal changes, it still changes its structure by increasing its reliability and resistance to external influences. In such conditions, the internal reform of the enterprise acts as a subsystem of internal management, which is systematically carried out at various stages of the organization's development.

The failure to take into account the essential foundations of economic processes at the level of enterprise management and the inability to coordinate one's interests with the interests of other business entities are the main obstacles to reforming enterprises and searching for new directions for their development. There are many reasons for the lack of readiness of the management of industrial enterprises to implement transformations, including: development strategy, basic market needs, old technocratic approaches to management, etc.

As a result, compared to smaller market players, industrial enterprises are much more vulnerable, since

their costs are much higher than those incurred on imported ready-made analogues, even including transportation and taxes. It is precisely the creative ability of enterprise managers that brings the following advantages:

- Increased adaptability,
- Increased quality of intra-organizational coordination;
- More rational mobilization of existing resources;
- Focus on strategic goals;
- Permanent and regular updating of personnel
- Growing demand for IT support;
- Further development of the control system.(3, p.4)

Of course, the reform itself does not automatically lead to various economic and managerial successes for the enterprise. The implementation of formal and endless changes, the lack of interest and initiative of personnel in the implementation of transformations, cannot provide significant results. It is also necessary to take into account that the reform of national enterprises is carried out mainly not at the stages of economic recovery, but to overcome the crisis.

The usefulness of reengineering is explained not only by the objective correctness of its constituent elements and its reliability as a whole, fundamental novelty, and practical significance, but also by analyzing the problems inherent in reengineering.

The change in the business environment surrounding the company necessitates an update to the concept of strategic planning. G. Ansoff and G. Milner were the first to realize the problem and the need for an active search for ways to solve it. The company's strategy must meet the rapidly changing conditions of the external environment. The bold concept of reengineering states that it offers managers, along with various problems, a procedure for making effective decisions.

In such a combination of serious deviations from strategy, threats to the existence of the company, and, in some cases, a feeling of managerial helplessness, the use of outdated techniques and methods to solve future development problems makes it possible to understand and properly appreciate the attractiveness of reengineering. Of particular interest are the findings published by Hillom and Collinsom on the results of a study of 73 large companies in Northern Ireland. This study is part of a broader research effort focusing on the use of incremental improvements and radical innovations in managing organizational change. Analyzing the results of this study and reviewing the related literature allows us to draw several critical theoretical conclusions about the situations in which business process management is most effective, or about strategies for implementing total (TQM) quality management and business process reengineering, among others. (14, p.23)

The main objectives of the survey conducted in Northern Ireland were: (a) to obtain some information (from within) on the perception, understanding, and use of BPR in Northern Ireland; (b) discuss the positioning of BPR in long-term organizational change strategies;

(c) explore the relationship between existing improvements in the form of TQM and radical innovation (BPR) as a change management approach. (6, p.12)

Some authors believe that reengineering can be successful in all three organizational situations: a company may be in crisis; it may be in a strong competitive position, but anticipates greater competitive pressure shortly; or it may be in a strong competitive position and wants to remain in a leading position in the future.

Many reengineering experts believe that the radical reengineering process must have a strategic context. Before a company selects a process for reengineering, a strategic analysis of the business, products, competition, and customers should be conducted. Once the company's current position is determined, a vision of some desired future positions can be developed. This, in turn, facilitates the selection of appropriate processes that will help the organization move towards this desired future state.

Both BPR and TQM are seen as essential elements of organizational change strategies in the short term. TQM seems to have emerged less as a model for competitive change than as a competitive imperative. The need for radical change, both now and in the future, seems to be well understood by large companies. (11, p.3)

Moreover, incremental improvement is seen as a vital foundation for business survival and change. Although some authors believe that the link between TQM and BPR is only continuous improvement, research has shown that other factors, such as cultural change and a focus on performance, are essential elements of both approaches. It also appears that when used in an integrated manner, BPR and TQM can drive organizational change.

Thus, the main feature that distinguishes the concept of reengineering is the synthesis of elements of previous concepts based on a complex approach, which has a much greater potential for increasing the efficiency of business processes. The attempt to deny the historical heritage that underlies the concept of business process reengineering contributes to the accusation that reengineering is based on exaggerated estimates, rather than on convincing analysis and proven benefits. (9, p.5)

Economic reengineering involves completely re-planning business processes using the latest management technologies, but without taking into account the existing order of business processes. However, not many companies have the opportunity to re-plan business processes (including financial ones) to start from a "clean slate": people, technology, and business knowledge cannot be so easily subjected to radical changes. In addition, during the transformation of a company, it is inevitable that new, unforeseen obstacles and new opportunities will appear. It should be noted that companies inevitably encounter difficulties when implementing both radical and gradual changes. This is mainly because many leaders (both Georgian and foreign companies) do not fully consider the connection between technology, practice, and strategy. Often, the development of a new product, updating the technology of work, changing the decision-making strategy, or the

communication system is considered separately. However, the implementation of these actions affects many aspects of the company's organization.

The recognition by managers of the crucial role of the interdependence of various elements of the business and its influence on the final result has led to the use of a fundamentally new method of analysis. When planning a strategy, all components of the business system should be considered and coordinated. Such interaction can also create several positive effects that enhance even small steps in change management. (16, p.4)

The change matrix is a way to identify the connection between different practices (of existing business processes). It is a graphic representation and consolidation, an intervention in the relationship between business processes, revealing the effect of synergy from this interaction.

Armed with this method, the leader of change in the company intuitively finds tricks and levers for a smoother transformation of the company. Once the new system is built, delegation of authority is easier for point-of-care execution and optimization. (10, p.41)

The matrix graphically depicts the organization's business practices, both positive and negative, and their impact on the business. The scoring system is designed for the practices that are most important to the company. The matrix analyzes the interactions between these practices and identifies potential difficulties in moving from the current group practices to the desired ones.

The use of the "change matrix" method consists of two stages: building the matrix and examining the matrix.

In addition to the "change matrix", there are four methods, each of which has its advantages and disadvantages: (a) the forced method is used to plan changes in conditions of high urgency for change. This method allows you to determine the sequence of changes and involves the use of force to overcome resistance; (b) the adaptive method of planning changes is to draw up a series of sequential measures, the implementation of which is planned over a long period. This process is slow, but it also has its positive sides - resistance is insignificant at any time. This technique allows for changes to be implemented in conditions where the proponents of change do not have administrative power; (c) the planning method is used in crisis conditions, when changes in the environment threaten the existence of the firm, time is strictly limited, and the organization is in crisis. In the conditions of the emergence of a crisis, planning should take into account that resistance gives way to support. Although the decisions are not yet clear, time pressure increases; (d) the resistance control method can be used when the time is longer than that required by the coercive method and less than that required by adaptive changes. When planning with this method, the duration of the change process fits into the available time. This feature is acquired by using a phased approach; (e) the change matrix is the most effective and efficient tool for analyzing changes and considers the organization from the point of view of a process approach. It consists of three matrices and a change process field and represents:

- 1) The current practice of organizational actions,

- 2) The desired set,
- 3) The transitional state that connects (1) and (2). (14, p.4)

Using the change matrix will allow leaders not only to resolve the dilemma of whether to continue radical or gradual changes in their organization, but also to manage the continuous improvement of the business effectively.

Finally, in summary, we should add the following: successful transformations of enterprises, especially those whose goal was large-scale, long-term, and competitiveness-oriented changes, tended to be carried out organically, rather than mechanically. Here, preliminary testing and model testing could have been used.

Conclusion

Finally, we should add the following as a summary: successful transformations of enterprises, especially those enterprises whose goal was large-scale, long-term, and competitiveness-oriented changes, tended to implement everything organically, not mechanically. Here, preliminary approval and testing of models could have been used.

Thus, it can be said that the transformation of business processes and changes in general are currently not an exception, but a rule of the successful functioning of the business system.

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